

Acceptance and Use of Learning Management Systems (LMSs) by Academic Staff in Jordan after Recovering from COVID 19 pandemic: Applying Technology Acceptance Model (TAM3)

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 17, 2024</p> <p>Accepted: July 19, 2024</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Learning Management Systems (LMSs), COVID19 pandemic, Technology Acceptance Model (TAM3)</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.12779716</p>	<p><i>Starting from the march of 2020, the outbreak of the COVID-19 caused Jordanian universities to close the campuses and forced them to initiate online teaching. Learning management system (LMS) is an important tool and well suited as a learning tool and activity in a university's high education. However, each institute has a different LMS tool that allows users (Management, Instructors, and Students) to use it for daily activity. This paper is interested in investigating the acceptance of Jordanian academic staff in using an LMS after getting back to work post the COVID-19 period. The study sample consisted of 382 Academic Staff of different ranks, selected randomly from all Jordanian universities, for the second semester, in the academic year 2019-2020. The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM3) has been adopted to identify the Acceptance and use of LMS. The questionnaire developed by the researchers was based on other past research studies. Simple linear regression was used to calculate the relationships between factors. The research results showed that there is a statistically positive effect of Perceived Usefulness, Perceived Ease of Use and Subjective Norm on Behavioral Intention; Perceived Ease of Use, Subjective Norm and Image on Perceived Usefulness; Subjective Norm on Image; and, Computer Self-Efficacy and Computer Anxiety on Perceived Ease of Use. This study indicates that we must always conduct workshops and training programs related to learning management systems and computers to enhance the usability of learning management systems among faculty members.</i></p>

Introduction

After the widespread effects of the Corona virus disease (COVID-19), education discussions globally have been focused on the topic of online education. The outbreak of COVID-19 caused most universities from all over the world to close their campuses and forced them to explore and adapt online teaching methods. Since March 2020, Jordanian universities have been on track and in the process of transforming completely to online learning. Following the government's instructions of "nonstop teaching and learning," most Jordanian universities have started online courses using various types of Learning Management Systems (LMS).

Before COVID-19, using an LMS in Jordan universities was more of a choice for academic staff; however, after COVID-19, the situation is very different, where it is now required of all the academic staff to make use of LMSs in teaching and learning processes. This paper is interested in investigating the acceptance of Jordanian academic staff in using an LMS after getting back to work post the COVID-19 period.

This study seeks to understand the extent to which academic staff accepts the use of LMSs and what factors may have a negative impact on the possibility of their continued use of LMSs in the future.

To answer these questions, the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM3) was applied in this study.

TAM3 was developed by [1] based on a revision of TAM and TAM2. It was designed for technological innovations similar to LMSs, and its model tests the factors that affect the acceptance of technology [1]. The TAM3 research model has been confirmed to work in real-world situations of IT implementations [2]. Additionally, TAM3 has been used to measure LMS user behavior in acceptance procedures ([3], [4]). This makes TAM3 an ideal framework to not only examine the factors that affect the acceptance of LMSs, but also to recommend actionable involvements for academic staff to increase the adoption and use of LMSs.

2. Literature review

Technology Acceptance Model (TAM3) has two core factors influencing Behavioral Intention (BI): Perceived Usefulness (PU), Perceived Ease of Use (PEU). The Factors which influence Perceived Usefulness (PU) are Subjective Norm (SN), Image (IM), Job Relevance (JR), Output Quality (OQ), and Result Demonstrability (RD). Perceived Ease of Use (PEU) is influenced by the following anchor variables ("Computer Self-Efficacy" (CSE), "Perceptions of External Control", "Computer Anxiety" (CA), and "Computer Playfulness" (CP)),

adjustment variables ("Perceived Enjoyment" (PE) and "Objective Usability" (OU)). Figure 1 shows the TAM3 model [1].

Figure.1 Technology Acceptance Model 3 (Venkatesh&Bala, 2008)

2.1 Conceptual Framework

Depending on the initial TAM3 model and previous literature, four factors (Subjective Norms (SN), Image (IMG), Computer Self-Efficacy (CS), and computer Anxiety (CA)) were used to analyze the academic staff acceptance and usage of LMS [5] determined that e-learning (SE) and (SN) were the most important vital variables were to influence the behavioral intention to use e-learning. [6] Developed a generally extended cap for e-learning (GETAMEL) to spot the foremost usually used external factors. The authors additionally terminated that SE, SN, enjoyment, CA, and knowledge are the foremost external factors usually used for TAM.

In short, in the current research conceptual framework the dependent variable contained is BI usage (BI is defined as "the person's subjective probability that he or she will perform the behavior in question" ([7], p. 288)). The independent variables are: PU is definite as "the degree to which a person believes that using a particular system would enhance his or her job performance" ([8], p. 320)) and PEOU is defined as: 'the degree to which a person believes that using a particular system would be free of effort' ([8], p. 320)). Among other variables usually used in frameworks such as these are, SN, which refers to the perceptions of the user to take attitudes of other people into belief when determining whether to use a system or not [7], Image, which is the degree to which use of an improvement is perceived to enrich one's status in one's social system [1], CSE, The degree to which an individual believes that he or she is capable of accomplishing specific tasks with computers [1], and Computer Anxiety (CA), It is the degree of anxiety, or even fear, of an individual when faced with the possibility of using computers [1]. Figure 2 shows the research conceptual framework.

Figure 2. The Research Conceptual Framework

2.2 Research Hypotheses

H1: Perceived Usefulness (PE) will have a positive influence on academic staff's Behavioral Intention of using the learning management system (LMS).

H2: Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU) will have a positive influence on academic staff's Behavioral Intention of using the learning management system (LMS).

H3: Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU) will have a positive influence on academic staff's Perceived Usefulness of the learning management system (LMS).

H4: Subjective Norm (SN) will have a positive influence on academic staff's Behavioral Intention of using the learning management system (LMS).

H5: Subjective Norm (SN) will have a positive influence on academic staff's Perceived Usefulness of the learning management system (LMS).

H6: Subjective Norm (SN) will have a positive influence on academic staff's Image of the learning management system (LMS).

H7: Image (IMG) will have a positive influence on academic staff's Perceived Usefulness of the learning management system (LMS).

H8: Computer Self-Efficacy (CS) will have a positive influence on academic staff's Perceived Ease of Use of the learning management system (LMS).

H9: Computer Anxiety (CA) will have a positive influence on academic staff's Perceived Ease of Use of the learning management system (LMS).

3. Research Methodology

3.1 Participants

The Participants in this research were faculty members from all 33 Jordanian public and private universities. Faculty members were from different departments of colleges, who were currently using a learning management system in Jordanian universities, at the time of this research.

3.2 Data Collection Method

The quantitative approach was used to collect data in this research, which was mainly done by using a survey questionnaire. Data was collected during the second semester of 2019/2020 by distributing electronic questionnaires among the faculty members of the Jordanian universities via their social media groups. 382 questionnaires were used, where the distribution of male recipients was about 70% and females, 30%. Their academic titles comprised of: assistant professor (57.6%), associate professor (23.5%), instructors (10.9%) and professor (7.8%). The table below gives a clear description of the participants in this study. Consequently, according to Hair et al. (2010), the sample size of this research (N = 382) was acceptable.

Table 1. Participants

Classification	Frequency	Percentage %
Gender		
Male	270	70%
Female	112	30%
Total	382	100%
Academic Position		
Professor	30	7.8%
Associate professor	90	23.5%
Assistant professor	220	57.6%
Instructor	42	10.9%
Total	382	100%

3.4 Instrument

The instrument used for this study includes two parts. The first one includes the academic staff demographic information: Gender, experience with learning management systems, university, faculty academic rank and type of the learning management system. The second part includes eight concepts of TAM3, BI, PU, and PEOU, which were adapted from [8] and [9] SN, adapted from [10]; IMG, adapted from [11]; CSE, adapted from [12]; and CA, which is adapted from [13]. SPSS 21 was used to analyze data, where a seven-point Likert scale was used to measure the instrument's items, ranging from "1" indicating "strongly disagree" to "7" indicating "strongly agree". Five experts checked face and content validity. The experts comprised of three educational technology professors and two Arabic language professors. According to the result of Cronbach's Alpha, the questionnaire reliability, which measured .842, was considered high.

4. Result and Discussions

Nine hypotheses were developed supported the initial TAM3 model developed by [9]. Each hypothesis was tested for significance and regression statistics were supported. Table 2 provides an outline of the regression information for each hypothesis. Larger beta values were validated for larger t-values and smaller p-values across all hypotheses. An in-depth discussion of each hypothesis follows the table.

Table 2. Hypotheses regression statistics

Hypothesis	Independent variable	Dependent variable	Df	F	t	P	Beta	R	R ²	Hypothesis supported
H1	PU	BI	1.379	784.382	6.39	.000	.821	.82	.67	Yes
H2	PEOU	BI	1.379	454.112	3.65	.000	.738	.73	.54	Yes
H3	PEOU	PU	1.379	707.277	1.78	.000	.807	.80	.65	Yes
H4	SN	BI	1.379	410.612	3.53	.000	.721	.72	.52	Yes
H5	SN	PU	1.379	392.350	3.87	.000	.713	.73	.50	Yes
H6	SN	IMAG	1.379	141.985	10.8	.000	.522	.52	.22	Yes
H7	IMAG	PU	1.379	114.829	7.51	.000	.482	.48	.23	Yes
H8	CSE	PEOU	1.379	113.212	4.57	.000	.480	.48	.23	Yes
H9	CA	PEOU	1.379	121.022	4.57	.000	.495	.49	.24	Yes

In this study, we tend to determine important relationships between all hypotheses. Supported the most factors listed on topof, we have discovered many recommendations to extend the quantity of LMS users.

Consistent with the previous analysis, the results of this study demonstrate this Perceived Usefulness (PE) and Perceived easy Use (PEOU) play a very important role in influencing the intention to use (LMS). Once the academic staff believes that using LMS would enhance their job performance which would be effortless, they would be more likely to use LMS. While some studies ([14]; [15]) It is reported that this position mediates the effect of perceived quality and perceived ease of use (PEOU) on activity intention, [13][7] failed to notice a full mediation effect of behavior intention.

We observed that there is a strong relationship between perceived ease of use (PEOU) and perceived usefulness (PU). Earlier studies showed that if an individual perceives a system to be easy to use, he/she is more probably to perceive the system to be helpful. Therefore, policymakers and universities have to target the perceived easy use of learning management systems. If academic staffs notice that an LMS is straightforward to use, they will be more probably to use it.

Subjective Norms have a positive influence on academic staff's behavioral Intention towards victimization an LMS. This research agrees with [7], who states that the perceptions of the user require attitudes of people into beliefs once determinant whether to use a system or not have a very important impact on the user's behavioral intention. Moreover, subjective norms have a positive influence on the academic staff's perceived usefulness of an LMS. Moreover, the study detected that subjective norms even have a positive influence on academic staff's Image of an LMS. Image, that indicates the degree to

which the use of improvement is seen to enrich an individual's position in a social system [1], encompasses a positive influence on academic staff's perceived usefulness of an LMS.

As explicit on top of, perceived easy use encompasses a high impact on users' behavioral intentions. This study infers that we must always increase users' computer Self-Efficacy (CE), and Computer Anxiety (CA). Therefore, workshops and training programs concerning LMSs and computers ought to be conducted to enhance the extent of usability of LMSs among academic staff.

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